

OBJECTIVES OF 5G-VINNI

Design an advanced and accessible 5G end to end facility.
Build several **interworking** sites of the 5G-VINNI end to end facility.

Provide user friendly **zero-touch orchestration**, operations and management systems for the 5G-VINNI facility.

Validate the 5G KPIs and support the execution of E2E trial of vertical use cases to prove the 5G-VINNI capabilities.

Develop a viable **business and ecosystem model** to support the life of the 5G-VINNI facility during and beyond the span of the project.

Demonstrate the value of 5G solutions to the 5G community particularly to relevant standards and open source communities with a view to securing widespread adoption of these solutions.

5G-VINNI FACILITY SITES

Main sites: E2E 5G-VINNI facility that offers services with well-defined Service Level Agreements.

Norway (Oslo, Kongsberg), UK (Martlesham), Spain (Leganes), Greece (Patras)

Experimentation sites: provide environments for advanced focused experimentation and testing.

Portugal (Aveiro), Germany (Berlin), Germany (Munich)

Moving Experimentation site: Satellite connected vehicle.

CAPABILITIES AND SERVICES

Capabilities

- » 5G NR RAN in 26GHz, 3.5GHz and other bands
- » 5G Core
 - › NSA in 2019, SA in 2021
 - › Rel'15 in 2019, SA in 2021
- » Slice types supported;
 - › eMBB
 - › URLLC
 - › mMTC (NB-IOT and LTE-M)
- » End-to-end Service Orchestration
- » Network Function Virtualization (NFV)
- » Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)
- » Satellite backhaul options
- » Interconnection and interworking among main facility sites

Services

- » Device Connection (eMBB, mMTC)
- » Network Slice as a Service (eMBB, URLLC, mMTC)
- » Customized Network Slice
- » Hosting of third party VNF in Slice
- » Distributed IoT Data Fabric Service in Slice
- » Integration of new non-5G-VINNI gNB
- » Integration of new non-5G-VINNI MEC node
- » Interworking with non-5G-VINNI facility sites
- » Testing services (KPIs)

5G VERTICALS INNOVATION INFRASTRUCTURE

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www.5g-vinni.eu

NORWAY (OSLO, KONGSBERG) provided by Telenor

- » Slicing (eMMB, URLLC, mMTC)
- » E2E Service Orchestration (Nokia)
- » NFVI (OpenStack), MANO (Nokia) and MEC (Nokia)
- » Four 5G gNBs (Ericsson, Huawei): 3.5 GHz (100 MHz BW), 26 GHz (800 MHz BW)
- » 5G Core (Ericsson)
- » Satellite backhaul option (GEO, Telenor)

UK (MARTLESHAM) provided by BT

- » Slicing (eMMB, URLLC, mMTC)
- » Service Orchestration (Nokia)
- » NFV MANO, NFVI and vEMS (Samsung)
- » MEC
- » 5G RAN incl. 3.5 GHz and 26 GHz (Samsung)
- » 5G Core (Samsung)

SPAIN (LEGANÉS) provided by Telefonica

- » Slicing (OSM extension)
- » Service Orchestration (OSM NBI)
- » NFV MANO (OSM) and NFVI (OpenStack)
- » SDN (ODL/ONOS)
- » Support for micro-VNFs
- » 5G RAN (SDR), low frequencies and 30-300GHz
- » Advanced monitoring and data-driven management
- » Edge computing (MEC and non-MEC)
- » 5G Core (possibly SBA-based)

GREECE (PATRAS) provided by Univ. of Patras

- » Slicing (eMMB, URLLC, mMTC)
- » Service Orchestration and hosting of VNFs
- » NFV MANO (OSM) and NFVI (OpenStack)+DPDK
- » 5G RAN open source radio 700-800MHz, 3.5-3.8GHz
- » 5G Core
- » NB-IoT, LTE-M, MEC
- » mmWave backhaul
- » GEANT connectivity

PORTUGAL (AVEIRO) provided by AlticeLabs

- » Service Orchestration (Altelabs)
- » NG-PON2-based 5G front/backhaul (Altelabs)
- » NFVI (OpenStack)
- » SDN (ODL)
- » Cloud RAN
- » MEC

GERMANY (BERLIN) provided by Fraunhofer FOKUS

- » 5G RAN prototype(s)
- » 5G Core (Open5GCore)
- » Edge cloud/e2e Orchestration (OpenBaton)
- » mmWave backhaul
- » Interconnection with remote islands in Betzdorf and Tokyo
- » Large scale events, Nomadic networks, Disaster Relief

GERMANY (MUNICH) provided by Huawei Germany

- » 5G NR SA RAN (Huawei) 3.5 GHz
- » 5G Core (Huawei)
- » MANO and NFVI (Huawei)
- » SDN (Floodlight)
- » V2I, V2P
- » MEC, Edge Computing
- » URLLC targeting Rel16/17
- » Sensor fusion enabled by 5G

SATELLITE CONNECTED VEHICLE provided by SES

- » GEO/MEO satellites
- » C/X/Ku/Ka-band
- » Satellite teleport
- » Satellite backhauling
- » Satellite 5G testbed node with SDN/NFV/MEC
- » Satellite interconnection with Berlin Facility site
- » eMMB, mMTC use cases